

Comparing PHP Collections

Anton Sukhachev

Abstract: This article compares different ways to create and use collections in PHP: arrays, Psalm annotation templates, monomorphic generics, and type-erased generics. Each approach is tested for type safety, IDE support, static analysis, memory usage, and performance. The results show that arrays use the least memory and are the fastest, but they do not provide type checks at runtime. The Psalm annotations help static analysis and IDE hints but still rely on documentation rather than real type checks. Monomorphic generics, implemented using the `mrsuh/php-generics` library, allow real type checking but lack IDE and static analysis support. The article concludes that arrays with annotations are best for simple cases, while Psalm annotations are more suitable for complex data structures.

Keywords: PHP, collections library, data structures, performance comparison, collections, generics

Let's imagine that we want to store a collection of `Item` objects:

```
<?php
namespace App\Entity;

class Item {
    public string $name = '';
    public int $value = 0;
}
```

Working with this collection we want to:

- PHP does a type checks to make sure collection only stores `Item` objects
- IDE makes hints about the type of `Item` objects in a collection
- static analyses tool can find type errors

I want to compare:

- [array](#)
- [Psalm annotation templates](#)
- [Monomorphic generics](#)
- [Type-erased generics](#)

Usage

Let's first compare usage.

Array

```
<?php

/** @var Item[] $collection */
$collection = [];
$collection[] = new Item();

/**
 * @param Item[] $collection
 */
function test(array $collection): array {}
```

pros

- easy to implement
- IDE makes hints about the type of `Item` objects in collection
- static analyses tool can find type errors

cons

- PHP doesn't check types

Psalm annotations

```
<?php

/**
 * @template T
 */
class Collection implements \Iterator
{
    protected \ArrayIterator $iterator;

    public function __construct()
    {
        $this->iterator = new \ArrayIterator();
    }

    /** @param T $item */
    public function append($item): void
    {
        $this->iterator->append($item);
    }

    /** @return T|null */
    public function current(): mixed
    {
        return $this->iterator->current();
    }
    ...
}
```

```
<?php
/** @var Collection<Item> $collection */
$collection = new Collection();
$collection->append(new Item());

/**
 * @param Collection<Item> $data
 * @return Collection<Item>
 */
function test(Collection $data): Collection {}
```

pros

- IDE makes hints about the type of Item objects in collection
- static analyses tool can find type errors

cons

- PHP doesn't check types

Monomorphic generics

```
<?php
class Collection<T> implements \Iterator
{
    protected \ArrayIterator $iterator;

    public function __construct()
    {
        $this->iterator = new \ArrayIterator();
    }

    public function append(T $item): void
    {
        $this->iterator->append($item);
    }

    public function current(): ?T
    {
        return $this->iterator->current();
    }
    ..
}
```

```
<?php

$collection = new Collection<Item>;
$collection->append(new Item());

function test(Collection<Item> $data): Collection<Item> {}
```

pros

- PHP does a type checks to make sure collection only stores Item objects

cons

- static analyses tool can't find type errors
- IDE doesn't make hints about the type of Item objects in a collection

Type erased generics

```
<?php
class Collection<T> implements \Iterator
{
    protected \ArrayIterator $iterator;

    public function __construct()
    {
        $this->iterator = new \ArrayIterator();
    }

    public function append(T $item): void
    {
        $this->iterator->append($item);
    }

    public function current(): ?T
    {
        return $this->iterator->current();
    }
    ...
}
```

```
<?php

$collection = new Collection<Item>;
$collection->append(new Item());

function test(Collection<Item> $data): Collection<Item> {}
```

cons

- PHP doesn't check types
- static analyses tool can't find type errors
- IDE doesn't make hints about the type of `Item` objects in a collection

Memory

Memory test is very simple.

It creates \$collection and puts Item objects into it count times.

For measurement I use [var_sizeof\(\)](#) and `memory_get_usage()`.

Items in collection: 0

type	var_class_sizeof(bytes)	var_sizeof(bytes)	memory_get_usage(bytes)
array(count: 0)	0	336	0
psalm(count: 0)	1,510	544	240
monomorphic(count: 0)	1,528	544	240
type-erased(count: 0)	1,512	544	240

Items in collection: 100

type	var_class_sizeof(bytes)	var_sizeof(bytes)	memory_get_usage(bytes)
array(count: 100)	0	7,728	12,248
psalm(count: 100)	1,510	7,936	12,432
monomorphic(count: 100)	1,528	7,936	12,432
type-erased(count: 100)	1,512	7,936	12,432

Items in collection: 1000

type	var_class_sizeof(bytes)	var_sizeof(bytes)	memory_get_usage(bytes)
array(count: 1000)	0	72,464	76,920
psalm(count: 1000)	1,510	72,672	77,104
monomorphic(count: 1000)	1,528	72,672	77,104
type-erased(count: 1000)	1,512	72,672	77,104

Items in collection: 10000

type	var_class_sizeof(bytes)	var_sizeof(bytes)	memory_get_usage(bytes)
array(count: 10000)	0	822,224	1,051,320
psalm(count: 10000)	1,510	822,432	1,051,560
monomorphic(count: 10000)	1,528	822,432	1,051,560
type-erased(count: 10000)	1,512	822,432	1,051,560

It's not surprising an array requires the least amount of memory.

Other approaches have roughly the same internal structure and require the same amount of memory.

Performance

I used [phpbench](#) to measure performance.

I think one of the big differences between all the solutions is the type checking. So I decided to try measure it.

How much faster will code with/without type checking?

```
PHPBench (1.2.3) running benchmarks...
with configuration file: /app/phpbench.json
with PHP version 8.1.3, xdebug , opcache 

\App\Tests\TypHintBench

    benchWithoutType.....R1 I6 - Mo240.713µs (±0.47%)
    benchWithArrayType.....R1 I70 - Mo247.663µs (±0.45%)
    benchWithMixedType.....R2 I59 - Mo249.293µs (±0.54%)
    benchWithClassType.....R1 I26 - Mo306.533µs (±0.48%)

Subjects: 4, Assertions: 0, Failures: 0, Errors: 0
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
-----+-----+
| benchmark      | subject                | set | revs | its | mem_peak | mode
| rstdev |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
-----+-----+
| TypHintBench | benchWithoutType      |     | 1000 | 100 | 674.272kb |
240.713µs | ±0.47% |
| TypHintBench | benchWithArrayType    |     | 1000 | 100 | 674.272kb |
247.663µs | ±0.45% |
| TypHintBench | benchWithMixedType   |     | 1000 | 100 | 674.272kb |
249.293µs | ±0.54% |
| TypHintBench | benchWithClassType   |     | 1000 | 100 | 674.272kb |
306.533µs | ±0.48% |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
-----+-----+
```

If the tests are correct, the difference between a function argument with class type and a function argument without a type is ~20%.

Conclusions

I have drawn some charts so you can compare all measurements in percentage. The results may vary slightly on different machines, but the percentage result should be the same

PHP MEMORY USAGE

If you are only using simple collections you can use `array` - it is very fast and requires little memory.

PHP doesn't support generic syntax and IDE can't make hints about the type of objects in a collection (yet),

but if you want PHP to do type checks at runtime you can test the [php-generics](#) library.

I think for now the best solution is a combination of `array` with annotations for simple collections and [Psalm annotation templates](#) for complex objects.

If you want to reproduce the tests result you can find the source code and instructions [here](#).